

1 **NOD2 and p53 mutually exert control over the cell cycle through CDK11a/CDK11b and CCNL2**
2 **(Cyclin L2), and this process involves a gene product that guides the Xist non-coding RNA to the**
3 **imprinting control region during development, CIZ1.**

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8 We describe here a phenomena involving interaction of the the tumor suppressor p53 and the
9 pattern recognition receptor NOD2 in a process regulating the cell cycle through the cyclin dependent
10 kinases CDK11A and CDK11B, the cyclin CCNL2 (cyclin L2), and a molecule that guides the non-coding
11 RNA Xist to the imprinting control region during development, CIZ1. This process likely involves MDM4, a
12 molecule that controls p53 regulation of the cell cycle (entry into mitosis).
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Results

We measured total transcription in multiple human systems to study regulation of the cell cycle by NOD2 and p53.

Figure 1: NOD2 control of CDK11a, CDK11b, and CCNL2.

a. GSE22611

n=3 HEK293 (human embryonic kidney cells; mock transfected)

n=3 HEK293 (stably expressing wild-type human NOD2)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
212401_s_at	3.78E-02	-2.7236635	-3.697278	-0.4013544	CDK11A///CDK11B	3760/54675	93.1
221427_s_at	7.54E-02	-2.1886356	-4.390049	-0.3378038	CCNL2	6540/54675	88.0
232274_at	4.05E-01	0.9024183	-5.906036	0.3014869	CCNL2	26159/54675	52.6

In human cells ectopically expressing wild-type NOD2, the expression of CDK11A/B and cyclin L2 was activated (Figure 1). Note that CCNL2 was also repressed by expression of NOD2 but to a significantly lesser extent (Figure 1).

Figure 2: p53 control of CDK11A, CDK11B, and CCNL2.

a. GSE171572

n=3 MCF10A wild-type (immortalized mammary epithelial cells)

n=3 MCF10A p53 *-/-* (knock-out)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
984	3.52e-02	0.0866	2.105594	0.1823784	785.86	CDK11B	4876/15028	67.8
728642	4.01e-02	0.1033	2.052443	0.2119742	497.49	CDK11A	5018/15028	66.6
81669	1.39e-04	0.1152	3.810639	0.4391235	1342.02	CCNL2	2132/15028	85.8

In human cells with genetically engineered deletion of the tumor suppressor p53, expression of CDK11A, CDK11B, and CCNL2 was lost, indicating p53 controls expression of CDK11A/B and CCNL2 (Figure 2A).

b. GSE162341

n=2 MCF10A wild-type (immortalized mammary epithelial cells)

n=1 MCF10A p53 R175H (human dominant negative mutation)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
81669	8.56E-01	1.187	-0.182014	-0.2161323	145.98	CCNL2	1418/15028	90.6
984	1.69E-01	1.585	1.375143	2.1794717	82.94	CDK11B	1425/15028	90.5
728642	2.90E-01	1.712	1.05728	1.8095635	66.15	CDK11A	1426/15028	97.2

In human cells expressing a dominant negative mutant of the tumor suppressor p53, expression of CDK11A and CDK11B was lost, while expression of CCNL2 was activated, supporting the conclusion that p53 controls expression of CDK11A/B and CCNL2 (Figure 2B).

3. CIZ1 expression dynamics suggest it is involved in regulation of CDK11A/CDK11B activity in the cell cycle by NOD2 and p53.

a. GSE22611

n=3 HEK293 (human embryonic kidney cells; mock transfected)

n=3 HEK293 (human embryonic kidney cells; stably expressing wild-type human NOD2)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
213976_at	6.27E-02	2.3297756	-4.20596	0.8485678	CIZ1	5588/54675	89.8
205516_x_at	3.00E-01	-1.1441117	-5.669796	-0.4375582	CIZ1	20455/54675	62.6

Similarly, expression of NOD2 in human cells resulted in differential expression of CIZ1, indicating NOD2 influenced expression of the CIZ1 gene, a molecule that functions in localization of the non-coding RNA Xist to the imprinting control region (ICR) (Figure 3).

4. CIZ1 and CCNL2, as well as a two separate molecules that functions as Xist localization components, SPEN and RBM15, can be retrieved as transcriptionally co-regulated interactants of NOD2 and CDK11A/B when querying whole transcription in multiple systems.

Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	% co-regulation transcriptome-wide
	CDK11A	728642	-320.0000	-320.0000	
	CDK11B	984	-0.1390	0.1825	
	NOD2	64127	-1.0678	0.0027	
1822	CIZ1	25792	0.3396	0.1579	89.9
16	CCNL2	81669	1.0612	0.0016	99.9
150	SPEN	23013	0.7259	0.0183	99.2
2390	RBM15	64783	0.2836	0.1874	86.8

Out of 18090 total transcripts

5. CDK11B, p53, and SPEN can be retrieved as transcriptional co-regulated interacts when querying total transcription in multiple systems using NOD2, CCNL2 and CIZ1, suggesting that NOD2, p53, CDK11A/B, cyclin L2 and Xist localization components SPEN and CIZ1 function together in some cellular transaction.

Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	% co-regulation transcriptome-wide
	CIZ1	25792	-0.4473	0.0022	
	NOD2	64127	-1.0852	0.0027	
	CCNL2	81669	-0.3934	0.0035	
188	CDK11B	984	0.5858	0.0013	98.4
1862	TP53	7157	0.2626	0.0757	89.6
770	SPEN	23013	0.4003	0.0618	95.7

Out of 17884 total transcripts

6. MDM4, the homologue of p53-binding partner MDM2, is a NOD2-regulated gene.

n=3 bone marrow derived macrophages from C57BL6/J mice (wild-type)

n=3 bone marrow derived macrophages from NOD2^{-/-} C57BL6/J mice

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
10357773	3.14E-05	-9.629622	2.41301	-0.8340187	Mdm4	2131/35557	94.0

7. MDM4 is an Xist co-regulated gene; the same transcriptional co-regulation query reveals MDM4 and CCNL2 are both co-regulated with Xist.

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	% co-regulation transcriptome-wide
	XIST	7503	-3.2	0	
299	MDM4	4194	0.2989	0.0172	98.3
154	CCNL2	81669	0.3451	0.0124	99.7

Out of 17830

Discussion

Together, the data indicate that the cyclin dependent kinases CDK11A and CDK11B, cyclin L2 (CCNL2), the tumor suppressor p53 and NOD2 function together with the non-coding RNA Xist and Xist localization components SPEN and CIZ1 to exert some cellular transaction that involves the MDM4, a p53-binding partner whose expression is controlled by NOD2.

References

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